

OUTLINE

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1. Introduction and overview

The Cheetah dataset contains geographical, industry and accounting information on three cohorts of mid-sized firms that experienced fast growth (i.e., average annual sales or employment growth greater than 20% for at least three years) during three growth periods: 2008-2011, 2009-2012 and 2010-2013. Mid-sized firms are defined by combining the EUROSTAT definition of medium-sized firm and the French definition of *Entreprise de Taille Intermédiaire* (ETI).

The uniqueness of Cheetah lies in the focus on this category of firms and its coverage in terms of countries. Cheetah includes 42,369 fast-growing mid-sized firms (FGMFs), which are located in 30 European countries and Israel. It is a unique source of data that offers to researchers new opportunities to study the growth dynamics of a relevant category of firms (i.e. mid-sized firms), which however has been almost neglected by the current academic literature on firm growth.

The European dimension of Cheetah makes the data infrastructure well suited to address research questions concerning the institutional determinants of firm growth and geographical agglomeration effects. Specifically, Cheetah allows to shed light on cross-country differences in the emergence of fast-growth mid-sized firms, as well as evaluating their performance across time. Evidence from the Cheetah dataset suggests a great variability in the number of mid-sized fast-growth firms across sectors and countries, with an interesting role of eastern European countries and regional-level factors.

The dataset is operated and maintained by Politecnico di Milano, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in Via Lambruschini 4/b, Milano, 20156, Italy. It is currently available in the .dta format (Stata).

Documentation:

- Link to metadata in RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/1/metadata>.
- Link to documentation in Zenodo: Guerini, Massimiliano (2019, July 16). Documentation of RISIS datasets: Cheetah. <https://zenodo.org/record/3337963>.
- Link to tutorial in Zenodo: Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering. (2019, August 2). RISIS DATASETS TUTORIALS: CHEETAH. <https://zenodo.org/record/3358993>.

2. Activities and Developments in the first reporting period

2.1. Maintenance

The planned Cheetah maintenance activities for the first two years of the project are summarized in the Table 1 (please see the D5.1 and D5.2 for details).

Table 1. Timetable M1-M24

M4	Identification of European medium-sized firms (for the cohorts 2011-2014, 2012-2015, 2013-2016, and 2014-2017).
M7	Data imputation (employees) and identification of the new cohorts of FGMFs.
M9	Download of accounting and ownership information for the FGMFs already included in Cheetah and the new cohorts.
M10	Geocoding and data cleaning.
M12	First update ready.
M24	Identification of European medium-sized firms (for the cohorts 2015-2018, 2016-2019, and 2017-2020).

As reported in Table 1, planned activities until M18 included: the identification of the new cohorts of European medium-sized firms (2011-2014, 2012-2015, 2013-2016, and 2014-2017), the data imputation of employees and the identification of the of FGMFs in those four cohorts, the download of accounting and ownership information for the FGMFs already included in Cheetah and the new cohorts, and geocoding and data cleaning. The primary source of data for these updating activities is Orbis. Updating is based on BvDID codes.

Most activities have been performed according to the workplan. Specifically, as to the identification of European medium-sized firms, we have downloaded data from Orbis on firms which meet the following criteria:

- Must be located in Europe (EU27, Norway, Switzerland and the UK).
- Must have a maximum turnover of 1,500,000 € OR maximum total assets of 2,000,000 € for at least one of the years 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014.
- Must have a number of employees greater than 49 OR lower than 5001 (or missing) for at least one of the years 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014.

A total of 6,474,510 firms were identified according to the criteria defined above.

In order to apply the employee threshold (i.e. number of employees between 50 and 4999) on observations with missing data (around 40% of observations) we used imputed data for the number of employees. Imputation used information on a firm's turnover, age, industry, and location. Eventually, after predicting the missing values for number of employees we applied the number of employee's threshold to define the final population of European medium-sized firms. We applied this threshold for the firms at the beginning of each growth period (2011, 2012, 2013, 2014) in order to assure that only medium-sized firms enter each growth observation period. The final population of medium-sized firms in the period 2011-2014 includes 438,320 firms.

After identifying the population of medium-sized firms, we selected those firms that experienced fast growth rates in the periods 2011-2014, 2012-2015, 2013-2016 and 2014-2017. To do so, we applied the definition of fast growing firms developed by OECD. According to this definition all firms with average annualized growth of greater than 20% over a three-year period, should be considered as high-growth firms. Growth is measured by either the number of employees or by turnover.

Following the above definition, we identified four new cohorts of FGMFs using both employment and turnover growth thresholds for each of the four observation periods (2011-2014, 2012-2015, 2013-2016 and 2014-2017). The final population of FGMFs in these new four cohorts consists of 51,841 firms.

We then downloaded from Orbis accounting information (balance sheet, income statement and cash-flow) for both old and new cohorts. For old cohorts (2008-2011, 2009-2012 and 2010-2013) we downloaded new accounting data for the years 2015, 2016, 2017 (years currently not included in Cheetah). For new cohorts (2011-2014, 2012-2015, 2013-2016 and 2014-2017) we downloaded from Orbis accounting data for the period 2010-2017.

As to geocoding, we downloaded complete addresses for the 51,841 firms identified in the new cohorts. Identification of latitude, longitude, NUTS regions and FUA is still ongoing. As to data cleaning, we double checked the firms included in the old cohorts with new information from Orbis. This allowed to identify a small number of duplicated and inconsistencies. As a result, the number of firms included in the old cohorts passed from 42,369 to 42,363. Table 2 shows the number of FGMFs included in all the seven cohorts.

Table 2. Number of firms for each cohort

Cohort	N. of firms included
2008-2011 (old)	17,435
2009-2012 (old)	24,992
2010-2013 (old)	16,083
2011-2014 (new)	18,271
2012-2015 (new)	18,738
2013-2016 (new)	20,757
2014-2017 (new)	21,226

The main delay concerns geocoding and the download of ownership information, which are taking longer than expected, so the update is expected to be ready at the end of M19 instead of M12. The activities concerning the second update will therefore start on M20 with the identification of European medium-sized firms for the cohorts 2015-2018, 2016-2019, and 2017-2020.

2.2. Deepening

Despite its potential for research and policy relevance, the current version of Cheetah has some limitations, as it does not allow an in-depth investigation of what drives the superior growth performance of fast-growing mid-sized firms, as well as their impact on job creation. From a policy perspective, it would be indeed of paramount importance to better understand whether growth actually leads to the creation of new employment, or whether it is driven by market consolidation strategies conducted through merge and acquisitions (M&As). An additional line of development is a better description of their innovation patterns, by looking, for instance, at the introduction of innovative business models.

The main aim of Cheetah development is therefore to increase the level of information depth concerning the firm-level characteristics of these firms. More specifically, development of Cheetah is aimed at:

- extending our understanding on the determinants and the mode of growth of fast growing mid-sized firms;

- providing a better characterization of their innovation patterns.

The first enlarged version of the Cheetah dataset is scheduled to be released in M30, while a second version with further updates and improvements is due by the end of the project in M42.

Activities has been performed according to the consolidated workplan presented in D9.1. Specifically, during the M18 period, deepening activities focused on the definition of new variables that capture start-ups' innovation patterns. In particular, we focused on innovation in business models, through the analysis of business documents, based on text classification. We decided to focus on a particular type of innovative business model that has emerged in the last years: platform-based businesses (e.g. Airbnb). Accordingly, firms included in Cheetah will be classified in platform-based business versus not platform-based, starting from the textual description of their business.

In order to automatize the classification, we explored a number of alternative strategies that combined information retrieval, data mining and machine learning techniques (e.g. classifiers starting from the description of the business). Particularly, to identify the most reliable source of information to for the classification, we performed 3 pilots tests. The evaluation of data sources took into account both the feasibility of obtaining the information in an automatic way as well as legal issues. To this aim, we sought business descriptions on Orbis, Lexis Nexis and Bloomberg databases. Among these data sources, we chose LexisNexis because it provides two major advantages. First, the pilots test showed that the data coverage from this data sources was satisfactory. Second, it allows us to include texts written by third parties, and not by the company itself. This reduces risks of subjectivity and biases.

In parallel to the pilot tests, we started a desk-study to identify the definition of platform-based business. Finding a well-accepted definition for platform business was fundamental for the following classification phases. In particular, the definition has been used to guide the manual classification of the business description that have been used to train the classification algorithm that will be applied to all firms in the Cheetah dataset in the following months.

In building the training set, our goal was to provide a sufficient number of documents to allow the algorithm to “learn” the most important keywords to classify a platform business. This documents should be similar to the documents that will be classified in the following months, in terms of structure, content and writing style. The training set developed for VICO (please see the VICO Overall Progress Report) shared all this features, thus, we used this training set for the training of the algorithm.

2.3. Access and usages

Current projects using the Cheetah dataset include:

- The analysis of the impact of mid-sized firms' fast growth on the traditional sectoral specialization, proxied in terms of employment, of Italian NUTS3 regions (Access ID 165);
- The analysis of growth determinants in mid-sized fast-growing firms (Access ID 111);
- The regional variation in the emergence of mid-sized fast-growing firms (Access ID 175).

Available empirical evidence from Cheetah has been presented during a policy event in Brussels at the end of 2019 (Camerani and Guerini 2019, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3520618>). Results suggest that Cheetah firms are quite widespread but not evenly distributed both across European countries (Figure 1) as well as within those countries (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Number and incidence of Cheetah firms by country

Figure 2. Distribution of Cheetah firms based on geographical coordinates

These firms also present different characteristics compared to the other mid-sized firms, in terms of geographical localization and sectoral specialization. The analysis also suggests that that even though these firms manage to be fast growing, they find it hard to maintain such performance over time. Finally, several economic, demographic, and knowledge-related regional factors are associated to the emergence of clusters of fast growing mid-sized firms in European regions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Clusters of Cheetah firms in selected European regions

More specifically, Camerani and Guerini (2019) analysed the factors that might be associated to the emergence of fast growing mid-sized firms using multivariate econometric analysis, by relating the number of fast growing mid-sized firms in a certain region/sector to country-, regional- and sector-level factors. These explanatory factors (source of data: EUROSTAT) include regional size (area in square km), density of mid-sized firms in the region/sector, regional population density, regional GDP per capita, regional human capital (share of people with a higher education degree), private and public regional R&D spending, and fixed effects at sectoral and country level (Northern countries, Southern countries, Eastern countries, UK).

The main results can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The number of fast growing mid-sized firms is positively related to regional population density and GDP per capita. This evidence seems to suggest the presence of agglomeration effects that make highly populated and richer regions a better environment to stimulate growth. These positive associations appear to be stronger in high-tech sectors.
- 2) Regional private R&D spending is positively associated to the emergence of these firms, while the public R&D spending exhibits an inverted-U shape relationship. In other words, a moderate level of public R&D spending seems to be positively related to fast growth; however, there are regions with very high levels of public R&D that exhibit lower performance.
- 3) On average, regional human capital does not play a significant role in the emergence of fast growing mid-sized firms in the different sectors. However, in high-tech manufacturing and services sectors we observe a positive and statistically significant relationship between the regional presence of skilled human capital and the emergence of these firms.

The regional level analysis will benefit from the integration of Cheetah with FirmReg and KNOWMAK, making possible to link the emergence of fast-growing mid-sized firms to indicators of scientific and technological knowledge production.

3. Outlook and next steps

As to maintenance, in order to complete the first update of Cheetah, two main activities will be performed in M18-M19. First, we will check whether a FGMF is not controlled (i.e. independent) by another firm/State in the period 2011-2017. To this aim, we will use the Orbis Ownership sub-database, which contains information on a firm's equity ownership structure (names of owners, direct and total ownership shares and type of owner). Based on the ownership shares and their type we will check whether a firm was independent in each year. A firm is considered independent if:

- the sum of the shares of individual shareholders is greater than 50% OR
- the highest share of shareholders that are firms/State is lower than 50%.

Second, we will conclude geocoding and update information on NUTS regions (2016 version) and Functional Urban Areas (FUAs).

As to development, during M18-M30 we will focus on firms' patterns of growth, with the aim to understand whether superior growth performance is associated to presence of specific investor types, and to assess the growth mode (organic vs. external) of fast-growing mid-sized firms in Cheetah. In order to identify the presence of the specific investor types, we plan to collect information on the ownership of these firms and to identify among main shareholders:

- private equity investors;
- large incumbent multinational firms.

In order to achieve this objective, we will mainly rely on the ORBIS database.

Furthermore, the collection of information on M&A activity of fast-growing mid-sized firms will allow distinguishing organic and external growth patterns. Information on M&A activity will be collected using the Zephyr database. This data collection effort will lead to the inclusion of additional variables in the Cheetah dataset, including the number of majority stake acquisitions made by fast-growing mid-sized firms during the entire observation period and additional information on the target companies (e.g., industry of operation and localization).

Updates and developments of Cheetah will be stored in RCF for direct user access. This process has to be developed (which data are stored, e.g. time coverage, how to deal with metadata, etc.).

4. List of milestones and Deliverables (WP5, WP9)

List of Deliverables

Contribution to overall deliverables for WP5:

D5.1 – Consolidated work plan on Maintenance [M6]

D5.2 – First interim report on Maintenance [M18]

D5.3 – Second interim report on Maintenance [M36]

D5.4 – Final report on Maintenance [M46]

Contribution to overall deliverables for WP9:

D9.1 – Consolidated work plan on datasets development [M12]

D9.2 – Interim documentation on new datasets development [M30]

D9.3 – Full documentation on developments made on RISIS core datasets [M42]

D9.4 – Policy briefs on new developments and their policy relevance [M42]

List of milestones and status

Number (WP)	Title	Due Date	Description	Status
MS9 (WP5)	Updated Cheetah 1	12	Updated database available for Access, reports on maintenance	Most tasks have been accomplished. Opening is foreseen in M19.
MS48 (WP9)	VICO and Cheetah enlarged versions with innovation patterns (version 1)	30	Data on innovation patterns (version 1) in VICO and Cheetah available for access	Pilot test concluded.
MS64 (WP5)	Updated Cheetah 2	36	Updated database available for Access, reports on maintenance	Activities will start in M23.
MS66 (WP9)	VICO and Cheetah enlarged versions with innovation patterns (version 2)	42	Data on innovation patterns (version 1) in VICO and Cheetah available for access	Activities will start in M30.

5. List of accesses

Applicant	Applicant institution	Project Title	Date
Roberto Camerani	University of Sussex (UK)	Regional variation in the emergence of fast growth firms.	June 25 th , 2020
Elena Prodi	University of Sussex (UK)	Mid-sized fast-growing Italian firms and structural change. An empirical investigation.	May 10 th , 2020
Anna Souakri	Ecole Polytechnique Paris (France)	Signals in entrepreneurial fundraising.	March 3 rd , 2020
Francesca di Pietro	Trinity College University (Ireland)	Relations between Crowdfunding and fast-growing firms.	February 2 nd , 2020
Bianca Potì	CNR-IRCrES (Italy)	The growth determinants in Fast growing firms (FGFs).	December 9 th , 2019